

D1.2 Data management plan

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Executive Summary

DigiBatt aims to reduce time and cost of battery testing using streamlined digital approaches for data exchange, virtual and hybrid testing methods and strategies for intelligent design of experiments. Methods developed in the project will be made available for the whole battery community to utilise. The project will generate various types of data which will be used to develop the new methods, as well as the code which constitutes the methods themselves.

The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling by describing what research data the project expects to use, data handling principles, and an assessment of what data can be shared with the public or why data cannot be open. Furthermore, it gives instructions on naming conventions and metadata structure.

Ethical aspects related to data collection, generation and sharing have been considered. All datasets will be uploaded, stored and handled in accordance with national and European rules on data protection and privacy. Metadata will be added to all datasets, and instructions on how to upload, store, publish and preserve research data is provided in this document.

DigiBatt will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant data repository to comply with the FAIR data principles.

Each dataset will be given a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata, and linked to the project acronym, full project name and grant agreement number. Publications and underlying research data will be linked, and a Creative Commons license will regulate reuse of DigiBatt research data. Data security arrangements are defined.

The DMP is a living document and will be updated as the project proceeds. The final version of the DMP will be made available at the end of the project. It will include instructions for how to access and reuse open research data from DigiBatt.

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
BibTeX	A reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licenses are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. ¹
CC BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, if they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CC0	CC0 enables scientists, educators, artists and other creators and owners of copyright- or database-protected content to waive those interests in their works and thereby place them as completely as possible in the public domain, so that others may freely build upon, enhance, and reuse the works for any purposes without restriction under copyright or database rights.
CC BY-NC	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new work must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don't have to license their derivative works on the same terms.
CC BY-SA	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, if they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to "copyleft" free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use.
CSL	Citation Style Language An open XML-based standard to format citations and bibliographies.
Deliverable type	R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports) DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. OTHER: Software, technical diagram
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DoE	Design of Experiments
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable data

¹ Creative Commons homepage: <https://creativecommons.org/>

GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation. Regulation (EU) 2016/679.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation An open-standard file format.
MARCXML	An XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
Research data	Refers to information, facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.
REST API	REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web services. API stands for Application Programming Interface
SSL/TLS	Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security These are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
Zenodo	Zenodo is a catch-all research data repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, make research results citable, and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal and hosted by the CERN cloud infrastructure.

1. Introduction and data summary

1.1 Introduction

DigiBatt will establish a novel, open, multi-scale digital toolbox to accelerate the testing and development of batteries. By STANDARDIZING, AUTOMATING, and ACCELERATING the battery testing process, DigiBatt will streamline testing workflows, improve the quality of results, and make digital battery testing accessible for the entire battery community. DigiBatt will realise these ambitious goals through:

- Universal, interoperable, semantic data models for battery data and metadata
- Digital twin infrastructure to link experimental testing with model-based virtual testing
- Strategies for intelligent design of experiments to reduce the number and duration of battery tests
- Reliable tools for predicting battery lifetime and safety within system-level infrastructure

During the project many types of data will be used and generated as described below.

1.1.1 Purpose of the document

The DMP provides an overview of research data the project is expected to generate or reuse, the types and formats of this data, and how this data is processed and stored to make them findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable, according to the principles of FAIR data management. The purpose of the DMP is to contribute to good data handling during the project's lifetime, and to describe how the research data will be curated and preserved.

1.1.2 Intended readership

In the project:

- Project participants who are responsible for, or in any way involved with, data collection and data handling can use this document for instructions on how to handle, store and process data.
- All project participants can use this document to get an overview of data collected in the project and how this is processed, stored and made accessible.

External audience:

- The **Data Summary** and **FAIR Data Management** sections can be used by all relevant stakeholders who are interested in DigiBatt related activities and research topics to get an overview of the data collected in the project, how to access this data, and, if applicable, how to re-use this data in their own activities.

1.1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

The DMP is not a fixed document but evolves during the lifespan of the project. Deliverable D1.2 is the initial version of the DigiBatt Data Management Plan.

- Deliverable D1.5 Revised data management plan, due month 18, will be a more detailed and updated version of the document.
- Deliverable D1.6 Final data management plan, due month 36 will be the final version of this document.

1.2 Data Summary

1.2.1 Purpose of the data collection and generation

The scope of the DigiBatt is to use battery simulation results, parameterisation data, testing data and operational data to create new hybrid, digital and physical battery testing workflows, simulation models and data structures. DigiBatt will focus on improving speed, accuracy and cost of battery testing for Li-ion batteries from cell scale up to system scale.

The main reasons for data collection in DigiBatt are:

- To provide input to physics-based and data-driven simulation models
- To provide input to routines for designing testing campaigns
- To benchmark new models and routines

Only data that is needed to perform project activities will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data unless this is necessary.

1.2.2 Data types, formats, and size

The DigiBatt will collect, generate and reuse various types of data. The data can fall under the broad categories of software, data and metadata. Many individual data entities produced in DigiBatt will be software based. There will also be data which includes parameter sets as well as data collected from experiments, simulations and field operations. These categories have been further subdivided as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Overview of data generated in the project

Category	Sub-category	Description	Data formats	Data size
Software	Data-driven simulation software	Computer code to run battery simulations where calculations are based on analysis of historical data.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Physics-based simulation software	Computer code to run battery simulations where calculations are based on physical laws.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Hybrid simulation software	Computer code to run battery simulations using both data-driven and physics-based calculations.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Data conversion software	Computer code to convert data into different formats so it can be interchanged between different hardware and software.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Data analysis software	Computer code to analyse data sets and extract	.py .m	kB - MB

		information from them		
Software	Digital twin	Computer code which interfaces between various software, hardware and data storage locations to provide a digital representation of a physical battery or battery system. A digital twin is a combination of all other types of software.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Application	A self-contained, standalone piece of software. An application could be of any type or combination of types of software.	.exe dockerfile	kB - MB
Software	Framework	Underlying coded structure used for deployment of other pieces of software.	.py .m	kB - MB
Software	Database	Structured set of data which can be queried.	.sql .xml .ttl	GB
Collected Data	Parameter sets	Set of parameters e.g. simulation input parameters, operational profiles.	.py .mat .json .xlsx	kB
Collected Data	Test data	Data produced as the result of physical or	.py .mat	MB - GB

		virtual testing. i.e. experimental results or simulation results.	Other proprietary formats which will be converted to common data formats	
Collected Data	Processed data	Data produced by processing test data.	.py .mat .json	MB
Collected Data	Operational data	Data obtained from operating batteries in the field.	.xlsx .csv .parquet .h5	GB
Metadata structures	Schema	Data structure describing properties required to describe other data sets.	.schema.json	kB
Metadata structures	Ontology	Set of concepts and properties related to a specific domain with links showing the connections between different ontology items.	.json .ttl	kB – MB
Metadata structures	Workflow	Description of steps to be taken in a process.	.txt .pdf	kB

1.2.3 Origin of data and provenance

Most software in the project will be built upon on existing software which is either available open-source and / or is owned as background by partners in the project. This is done to ensure that the developments of the project extend the current state-of-the-

art and will continue to be used after the end of the project. More information on specific background brought into the project can be found in Attachment 1 of the Consortium Agreement.

DigiBatt will collaborate with other EU-funded research projects to re-use data as far as possible. This will help to avoid duplicating work and accelerate the development of models and tools within the project. New collected data will be generated within the project when this data does not exist elsewhere for the specific cell types under consideration and the specific quantity and combinations of data required to develop the numerical testing methods. Metadata structures generated in the project, in particular schemas and ontologies will build on previous work on related ontologies and will be extensions of these.

1.2.4 Potential reuse of data

Within DigiBatt we aim to make the work we do as reusable as possible outside of the project. As much as possible, code and data will be made available under an open-source licence. This will allow reuse of the methods developed by stakeholders external to the project, including researchers in battery fields, battery manufacturers and battery system integrators. This could be reuse of software or reuse of collected data to develop and benchmark new simulation models. The open-source nature of the work will allow adaptations to the software so that methods can be applied to new battery chemistries in the future. Ontologies developed in the project will be connected to existing ontologies in related fields and can be applied to new data collected in other projects.

Potential stakeholders and target groups for data re-use include:

- EU-funded research projects
- Battery researchers and engineers
- Software developers
- Battery-related corporations and SMEs

1.2.5 Data storing in active project – project platform

Datasets in DigiBatt will be stored in a SINTEF SharePoint project site. This will be the project's online working and collaboration area during the 36 months the project is active. Large tabular datasets will be integrated into a shared SQL database for efficient querying and retrieval of data.

All partners will be responsible for uploading datasets they have collected/generated during the project. Each dataset will be catalogued in a Database providing an overview of all datasets in the project, as well as uploaded to a dedicated research data folder in

the SharePoint site. All datasets will use standard SharePoint version control and access control is available to enable limited access to certain types of data.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- Project ID (Grant No)
- Data Owner
- File name
- Version
- WP number
- File type
- Datetime
- Dissemination level
- Keyword
- Language
- Brief description of data i.e., objective, prevailing conditions during data acquisition e.g., temperature etc., nature of data (field or lab)

We follow the guidelines from the W3C for sharing tabular data/metadata

www.w3.org/TR/2015/REC-tabular-data-model-20151217/https://www.w3.org/TR/2015/REC-tabular-metadata-20151217/

1.2.6 Repositories

DigiBatt will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant repository to comply with the FAIR principles. All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the DigiBatt Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/digibatt>. In addition, the project will upload other datasets (not directly linked to publications and deliverables) with dissemination level "Public" and make them openly accessible via the repository.

GitHub will also be widely used for collaborative development and sharing of software generated in the project. DigiBatt will have an organisation on GitHub which will contain software repositories which are only directly relevant to the project (e.g. json-ld data knowledge graph for data collected in the project). Software intended to be used after the project and extensions to existing software will be hosted in specific software repositories.

Both Zenodo and GitHub allow for easy coupling of code repositories to datasets and the generation of DOIs to make the code citeable. Scientific publications based on or derived from these modelling codes or underlying datasets will be open-access and will be linked to the relevant GitHub repositories via citation of the linked Zenodo DOI.

Free-of-charge hosting for software development and version control using Git is granted by GitHub. Furthermore, the distributed version control and source code

management functionality of Git is offered, and access control and several collaboration features such as bug tracking, feature requests, task management, and wikis for every project are provided. Free GitHub accounts are commonly used to host open source projects.

1.2.7 Instructions for storing datasets

Instructions on how to store datasets on SharePoint, Zenodo and GitHub are given below:

Table 2 Data storage instructions

Upload instructions - DigiBatt Sharepoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Please upload all DigiBatt data sets to the 10_Data folder on sharepoint • Create a new folder with this naming convention (for details see 2.1.5): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>Descriptive text HEU_DigiBatt_PARTNER_YYYYMMDD_UniqueDataNumber</i> • Upload the files into this directory (as far as possible, use open, non-proprietary formats like parquet, json, hdf5, csv, etc.) • Add a mandatory json metadata description as described in section 1.2.5 above
Zenodo
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to Zenodo. To do this you must complete the following steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files ○ Click on <i>DigiBatt Community</i> link above, or search for "<i>DigiBatt Community</i>" under the "Communities" tab at the top of the Zenodo site ○ On the Community site, click the green "New upload" button in the top right corner ○ Enter requested data and confirm the upload. ○ Remember to add the European Commission community in the box labelled "communities". You can use the search function to locate the community and add it. The data will then automatically be uploaded to both communities, so you don't have to do it twice. • Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest. • Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets collected/generated by them. If needed, the DigiBatt data manager will supply assistance.
GitHub
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software generated in the project classified as "Public" should be made available via a public repository in GitHub as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest.

- Software should be clearly documented and include a README describing usage instructions.
- Repositories containing software generated in the project classified as "Public" should be archived in Zenodo to create a DOI and fulfil FAIR requirements. Instructions for archiving a git repository in Zenodo can be found here: <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/referencing-and-citing-content>

2. FAIR Data Management

DigiBatt will manage data in accordance with the principles of FAIR data management² (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data). The project aims to maximise access to, and re-use of research data generated by the project. At the same time, there are datasets, or parts of datasets, generated in this project that cannot be shared to protect business sensitive information.

Appendix A: DigiBatt Datasets provides a current overview of the expected types of data in DigiBatt and their accessibility.

2.1 Making data findable

2.1.1 DigiBatt Community in Zenodo

DigiBatt will use the Zenodo repository as the main tool to make our research data findable in accordance with the FAIR data principles.

A *DigiBatt* community has been established in the repository, and the project will upload all our public datasets and deliverables as well as scientific publications to this community. This will ensure harvesting of project results by OpenAire and provide maximum findability. All uploads will be enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number, Project Name and Acronym. The repository provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

2.1.2 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default be as follows:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Creator (Name and ORCID)
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

²

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2_020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

- Project name
- Grant Agreement number

2.1.3 Versioning and Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

Zenodo provides DOI versioning of all datasets uploaded to their communities, which allows us to edit and update the uploaded datasets after they have been published. This also allows us to cite specific versions of an upload and cite all versions of an upload.

2.1.4 Approach to search keywords

Each partner who collects and generates public datasets will be responsible for uploading these to the repository and to assign specific search keywords relevant for these datasets. Dataset specific keywords must be descriptive to the content of the dataset. In addition, the project has defined a set of general keywords that apply to all public datasets, scientific publications and public deliverables. These are as follows:

- DigiBatt
- Battery
- Testing
- Digitalisation
- HEU

2.1.5 Naming conventions

Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

Descriptive text_HEU_DigiBatt_PARTNER_YYYYMMDD_UniqueDataNumber

Descriptive text_HEU_DigiBatt_PARTNER_YYYYMMDD_UniqueDataNumber

Explanation of the naming convention:

- "Descriptive text" refers to a *short* description of the content of the dataset (see example)
- "PARTNER" refers to the short name of the partner who generated the data
- "YYYYMMDD" refers to the date the data was generated
- "UniqueDataNr" is a short (6-character) unique identifier that can be generated here: <https://shortunique.id/>

Example of dataset name:

MJ1 cycling data_HEU_DigiBatt_SINTEF_20240413_cwopqk

M50 EIS data_HEU_DigiBatt_DLR_20240315_6eOK8g

2.2 Making data accessible

The EU's Open Science Policy aims to make research data generated by Horizon Europe projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protection of personal or sensitive data due to privacy concerns and/or commercial or security reasons.

All public datasets, scientific publications and deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and made openly available, free of charge. Publications and underlying data sets will be linked through use of persistent identifiers (DOI versioning). Data sets with dissemination level "confidential" (non-anonymous datasets) will not be shared due to privacy/security/ethical concerns. Potentially, some datasets might be restricted due to protection for commercial exploitation. If such cases arise during the project, this will be informed in the final version of the DMP.

Metadata including licences for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application. No specific software or hardware is needed to access and reuse the data.

Appendix A: DigiBatt Datasets provides a list of types of datasets expected to be generated in DigiBatt and their planned accessibility. This list constitutes the first version of dataset description, and we recognise that it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets currently remain unknown, e.g. size of the datasets. An updated version of the list containing all dataset details will be provided at the end of the project.

2.3 Making data interoperable

Zenodo uses JSON schema as the internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

2.4 Reusable data

DigiBatt will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using appropriate licences.

2.4.1 Recommended licences

For Collected Data DigiBatt will use Creative Commons licences (CC), which are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC BY license will be applied for public DigiBatt collected research data generated during the project. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC 0 or more restrictive licenses as CC BY-ND, which does not allow derivations.

For Software and Metadata descriptions DigiBatt will use appropriate licences which are compatible with the policy of being as open as possible, as closed as necessary. This may include licences such as GPL 3, MIT, BSD-clause 3.

Application of licences will be assessed on a case-by-basis in close collaboration with the Coordinator, Innovation Manager and partners concerned.

2.4.2 Availability and longevity of DigiBatt research data sets

Public (anonymous) data

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available at the latest by the publication date of the article. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved and accepted by the EC. For other public datasets not directly linked to a scientific publication or deliverable, such datasets will be made available upon assessment by the responsible partner that it is ready for publishing, and in the final month of the project at the latest.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will not be reusable due to privacy/security concerns.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime stated by the host laboratory CERN. If Zenodo has to close their operations, they have provided a guarantee that they will migrate all content (including metadata) to other suitable repositories.

Confidential (non-anonymous) data

All non-anonymous data will be deleted at the end of the project.

3. Other research outputs

Research outputs from DigiBatt include not only raw testing data, but also battery simulation frameworks, data processing software, and dashboarding applications. The source code for these software components is hosted and maintained on GitHub (and/or comparable git-based platforms) for version control and collaborative development. Key considerations and recommendations for the management of these outputs include:

- **Versioning strategy:** By default, the [semantic versioning strategy](#) is recommended for software development in the project. In some cases where regular releases are planned at regular intervals, [calendar versioning](#) may also be acceptable.
- **Documentation:** [Sphinx-based documentation](#) is recommended for software developed in the project.
- **Continuous integration and delivery:** [CI/CD workflows](#) are recommended to be implemented via GitHub actions (or similar) to ensure the robustness and resilience of project software.
- **Licensing:** By default, software developed within DigiBatt should be licensed with a permissive open-source license such as GNU GPL v3.0, Creative Commons, or MIT licenses. More restrictive licences may be acceptable in cases where a compelling interest for exploitation can be demonstrated.

This structured approach facilitates effective software development, enhances project efficiency, and promotes wider dissemination of research outcomes.

4. Allocation of resources

4.1 Costs

DigiBatt uses standard tools and a free of charge research data repository. The costs of data management activities are limited to project management costs and will be covered by allocated resources in the project budget.

Long-term preservation of the public data is ensured through Zenodo and GitHub. Other resources needed to support reuse of data after the project ends will be solved on a case-by-case basis. The estimated curation and storage costs are 6000 EUR. The costs were included in the project budget.

4.2 Data Manager

Dr. Sridevi Krishnamurthi – Research Scientist at SINTEF - will be responsible for the data management and quality assurance.

5. Data Security

In this chapter, the security features of the research data infrastructure used to store and handle data in DigiBatt project are described.

5.1 Active Project – Data security as specified for SINTEF SharePoint

SINTEF SharePoint is the online collaboration platform used in DigiBatt project. A dedicated project site has been established on this platform, accessible only by the partner representatives in the consortium. Furthermore, a dedicated folder for research datasets is set up, allowing for stricter access control than the main project site.

The DigiBatt Sharepoint site has the following security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only). Further access restrictions on specific folders could if necessary be enabled.
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and the SINTEF SharePoint site.
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents and/or registers possible manipulation of data.

Documents and elements in the SINTEF SharePoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions, based in Ireland and the Netherlands. There will be no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA and associated countries³.

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. As a baseline, all project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF's ICT policy, unless otherwise agreed in contracts and data processing agreements.

5.2 GitHub – Data security

The security settings for GitHub are:

- **Versions:** GitHub retains multiple versions of files, allowing users to access previous versions or restore deleted files through version control features like Git.
- **Replicas:** GitHub employs redundancy and replication across multiple data centres to ensure data availability and integrity in case of hardware failures or disasters.
- **Retention Period:** GitHub stores data as long as the user's account remains active. If an account is deleted, GitHub retains certain data for a period according to its data retention policies or legal obligations.

³ EEA = Norway, Iceland, Liechtenstein

- **Security Measures:** GitHub implements various security measures to protect user data, including encryption, access controls, monitoring, and vulnerability management.
- **Access Controls:** GitHub allows users to control access to their repositories through settings such as public, private, or restricted access to specific collaborators.
- **Succession Plans:** GitHub provides options for transferring ownership of repositories or organizations in case of changes in ownership, such as succession planning or transferring ownership to another user or organization.

5.3 Repository - Data security

The following list describes the security settings for Zenodo:

- **Versions:** Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.
- **Replicas:** All data files are stored in the CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- **Retention period:** Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. The host laboratory of Zenodo CERN, has defined a lifetime for the repository of the next 20 years minimum.
- **Functional preservation:** Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- **File preservation:** Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- **Fixity and authenticity:** All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- **Succession plans:** In case of closure of the repository, a guarantee has been made from Zenodo to migrate all content to suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

6. Ethical Aspects

DigiBatt partners are obliged to fully comply with the regulations set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁴. In addition, DigiBatt comply with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless country in which research is carried out.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research. SINTEF follows the Vancouver Recommendations for publication of scientific work.

Currently, no ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data generation and sharing have been identified. Ethical and legal aspects related to research data generated by the project will be considered as the work proceeds.

6.1 Contact information

An e-mail address is by definition personal information and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in DigiBatt SharePoint Site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the SharePoint invitation the participants consent to use and store their e-mail address for the purpose of online collaboration in the project. The email-addresses will be deleted when access to the project area is no longer needed (1 year after project closure). SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling our SharePoint platform.

6.2 Pictures and videos for communication purposes

DigiBatt will collect pictures and videos for use in communication activities (website, newsletter, social media). Such data will only be collected with prior consent from the people involved and only used for as long as consent is given. Pictures and video can contain personal data if an individual is the focus of the image or video. Examples include: 1) pictures/video of individuals stored together with personal details (e.g. identity cards); 2) pictures/video of individuals posted on the project website along with biographical details; 3) individual images published in a newsletter. Examples of

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

pictures and video that is unlikely to contain personal data are: 1) pictures/video where people are incidentally included in an image or are not the focus (e.g. at a big conference/workshop); 2) images of people who are no longer alive (the GDPR only applies to living people,).

When collecting pictures and video DigiBatt will follow established guidance and best practice on collecting and processing such data to ensure that we adhere to the legal requirements. Under no circumstances will pictures containing personal information be publicly shared without the subject's explicit consent.

7. Conclusions

This document sets out the data management procedures and plan for data management in the DigiBatt project. It is a starting point from which further discussions will be held within the consortium regarding how we handle data. The list of data produced in the projects will be updated throughout the project and in future will be stored in a machine readable format. This document serves as a reference for all DigiBatt consortium members.

8. References

European Commission. *H2020 Programme. Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.0, 26 July 2016

European Commission. *Horizon 2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. Version 3.2, 21 March 2017

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC

Appendix A: DigiBatt Datasets

This appendix lists tentative anticipated dataset outputs from the DigiBatt project, including software, metadata, parameter sets etc. Category definitions along with data formats and size ranges are shown in Table 1.

This table has been generated from the DoA. Task leaders have been listed as responsible partners unless clearly stated in the DoA that a particular partner was responsible for a particular dataset.

It is expected that this table will evolve throughout the duration of the project. Entries in this table are subject to change, in particular with respect to the partner responsible and sensitivity levels.

Table 3 DigiBatt Datasets. PU – Public, SEN – Sensitive, P – Project participants, R – Researchers, I – Industry

No.	Task	Dataset	Category	Subcategory	Partner Responsible	Provenance	Sens. Level	Utility
1	2.1	Standard vocabularies for battery test data	Metadata Structure	Schema	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
2	2.1	Ontologies for battery test equipment, digital models and workflows	Metadata Structure	Ontology	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
3	2.1	Safety relevant parameters	Metadata Structure	Schema	VIF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
4	2.2	Algorithms to extract safety relevant parameters	Software	Data analysis software	VIF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
5	2.2	Shared digital interfaces for data exchange between equipment and digital models	Software	Data conversion software	UOXF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
6	2.3	Common database infrastructure for automated data exchange	Software	Database	SINTEF	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
7	2.4	Methods for exchange between digital twin and database	Software	Data conversion software	SINTEF	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
8	3.1	Digital twin framework	Software	Framework	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
9	3.2	Physics based models	Software	Physic-based simulation software	UOXF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
10	3.3	Workflows and decision structures for automatic design and triggering of tests	Metadata Structure	Workflow	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R, I

11	3.3	Methods for digital twin to respond to semantic queries	Software	Data Conversion Software	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
12	3.3	Complete digital twin model	Software	Digital Twin	UOXF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
13	3.3	Containerised digital twin for full battery systems	Software	Application	UOXF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
14	4.2	Automated testing framework	Software	Framework	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R, I
15	4.2	Machine learning models	Software	Data-driven simulation software	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R, I
16	4.3	Safety testing campaigns	Metadata Structure	Workflow	VIF	Generated	PU	P
17	4.3	Cell and module safety test data	Collected Data	Test data	CORVUS	Reused	SEN	P, R
18	4.3	Extracted safety parameters	Collected Data	Parameter set	VIF	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
19	4.4	Calendric and cyclic ageing test campaign designs	Metadata Structure	Workflow	FZJ	Generated	PU	P
20	4.4	Calendric and cyclic ageing test data	Collected Data	Test Data	FZJ, DLR, CORVUS	Generated	PU	P, R
21	4.4	Parameterised battery models	Collected Data	Parameter set	FZJ	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
22	4.4	Optimised battery campaigns for ageing testing	Metadata Structure	Workflow	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R, I
23	5.1	Computational framework to extract physical parameters from experimental data	Software	Framework	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R, I
24	5.1	Expectation propagation and Bayesian Optimisation parameter estimation algorithm	Software	Data analysis	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R, I
25	5.1	Computational framework for parameter estimation using FZJ in house code and ML methods	Software	Framework	FZJ	Generated	SEN	P
26	5.2	Experimental workflow to collect tailored sequences of electrochemical measurements	Metadata Structure	Workflow	DLR	Generated	PU	P

27	5.2	Results from sequences of electrochemical measurements	Collected Data	Test data	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R
28	5.2	Sensitivity analysis of different input profiles to aid experimental design	Collected Data	Processed data	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R, I
29	5.2	Active DoE approach adapted to parameter estimation	Metadata Structure	Workflow	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
30	5.2	Parameters for physical modelling obtained by electrochemical measurements and digital workflows	Collected Data	Parameter set	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R, I
31	5.3	Cell tear down and characterisation results	Collected Data	Test data - Experimental	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R
32	5.3	Microstructural data analysis with ML based techniques	Collected Data	Processed data	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R
33	5.3	Thermal parameters and characterisation data	Collected Data	Processed data	UOXF	Generated	PU	P, R
34	5.4	Parameterised ECM models	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R
35	5.4	Experimental routines to parameterise ECM models	Metadata Structure	Workflow	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
36	5.4	Digital methods for online parameterisation of ECM models	Metadata Structure	Workflow	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
37	5.4	Parameters extracted from operational data using AVL's data analytic framework	Collected Data	Parameter set	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
38	5.4	Methods to generalise performance models from cell to module level	Software	Hybrid simulation software	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
39	5.4	Module test data from conventional characterisation	Collected Data	Test data	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
40	5.4	Module test data from new test methods	Collected Data	Test data	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
41	6.1	Methods for accelerated lifetime assessments of cells	Metadata Structure	Workflow	AVL	Generated	PU	P, R, I

42	6.1	Raw data from battery cell experiments	Collected Data	Test data	CORVUS	Reused	SEN	P
43	6.1	Raw data from battery cell experiments	Collected Data	Test data	DLR	Generated	PU	P, R
44	6.1	Raw data from battery cell experiments	Collected Data	Test data	FZJ	Generated	PU	P, R
45	6.1	Methods for feature extraction from long timeseries data	Software	Data analysis software	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
46	6.1	Operational data from maritime applications	Collected Data	Operational data	CORVUS	Reused	SEN	P
47	6.1	Extracted features which are leading indicators of degradation	Collected Data	Processed data	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
48	6.1	Reduced order models from higher order models created in WP3 and WP5	Software	Hybrid simulation software	AVL	Generated	PU	P, R, I
49	6.1	Behaviour models for lifetime as function of influencing parameters	Software	Hybrid simulation software	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
50	6.1	System-level I/O interfaces	Software	Data conversion software	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
51	6.1	Battery pack model requirements for system level testing	Metadata Structure	Workflow	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
52	6.2	Failure mode and degradation predictions	Collected Data	Processed data	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P
53	6.2	Model based estimation of surge and steady-state short circuit current at various conditions	Collected Data	Processed data	SINTEF	Generated	PU	P, R, I
54	6.3	Variant management framework	Software	Framework	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
55	6.4	Online HiL assessments using models developed in project	Collected Data	Processed data	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
56	6.4	BMS interface requirements	Metadata Structure	Schema	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
57	7.1	Calibrated models for specific battery packs and mission profiles	Collected Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
58	7.1	Cell configurations per drivetrain specifications	Metadata Structure	Schema	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
59	7.1	Cell to pack sizing tool for specifications	Software	Application	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I

60	7.1	Maritime system-level simulation parameters	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
61	7.1	System level specifications for different vehicle classes	Metadata Structure	Schema	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
62	7.1	Module scale test results for comparison with digital twin	Collected Data	Test results	VIF	Generated	SEN	P
63	7.2	e-drivetrain standard model interfaces for use-case system validation for different EV applications	Metadata Structure	Schema	VUB	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
64	7.2	Powertrain platform for use-case system validation for different EV applications	Software	Framework	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
65	7.2	Interface between digital twin and operational profiles for maritime applications	Software	Data conversion software	CORVUS	Generated	PU	P, R, I
66	7.2	Routines for field data processing and missing data imputation	Software	Data analysis software	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
67	7.2	Pack level parameterised simulation model	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	PU	P
68	7.2	Development and calibration of e-drivetrain components	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	PU	P
69	7	Use case scenarios for EVs	Collected Data	Parameter set	AVL	Generated	SEN	P
70	7	Example operational profiles	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
71	7.2	Virtual simulator platform in Matlab / Simulink	Software	Framework	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
72	7.2	Calibrated Co-simulation models	Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
73	7.3	System level virtual test plan	Metadata Structure	Workflow	VUB	Generated	PU	P
74	7.3	Digital twin in the loop testing results	Collected Data	Test data	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
75	7.3	Safe operating windows for V, I, T	Collected Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
76	7.3	Battery in the loop testing results for different EVs	Collected Data	Test results	VUB	Generated	SEN	P

77	7.3	Battery and module testing results for maritime applications	Collected Data	Test results	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
78	7.4	Battery pack responses and ageing impact	Collected Data	Test results	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
79	7.4	Virtual battery behaviour for different profiles	Collected Data	Test results	VUB	Generated	SEN	P
80	7.4	Workflow for automated identification of most effective mission profile	Metadata Structure	Workflow	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
81	7.4	Most effective mission profile to shorten testing	Collected Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
82	7.4	System-level test results of developed tools for maritime applications	Collected Data	Test data	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
83	7.4	Safety margin and selection criteria for critical missions	Collected Data	Parameter set	VIF	Generated	SEN	P, R, I
84	7.5	Comparison of impact of critical mission choice	Collected Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
85	7.5	Dynamic correlation analysis results	Collected Data	Parameter set	VUB	Generated	PU	P, R, I
86	7.5	Digital twin outputs for the operational data	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
87	7.5	Digital twin performance requirements	Collected Data	Parameter set	CORVUS	Generated	SEN	P
88	7.5	Real field data from EV applications	Collected Data	Operational data	AVL	Reused	SEN	P

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